

The Development of Green Technologies in Europe

Between 2014 and 2021 it decreased by 25.26%

The European Innovation Scoreboard-EIS calculates the percentage of technological innovations that are connected to the environment on the total number of patents. Technological innovations related to the environment refer to a set of elements such as environmental management, optimization of water resources and the fight against climate change. This indicator can calculate the impact of technological innovation on environmental sustainability. The goal of making the production system more sustainable from an environmental point of view is also achieved through technological innovation.

Ranking of countries for green technological innovations. Bulgaria is in first place for the value of sustainable technological innovation with a value equal to 172.29 equal to Malta. Denmark is in second place with a value of 164.07 units and from Estonia with a value of 137.35 units. In the middle of the table are Luxembourg with an amount of 64.69, followed by the Czech Republic with an amount of 64.51 and Italy with a value of 59.03 units. Romania closes the ranking with a value of 14.66 units followed by Cyprus and Montenegro with a value of 0.00 units.

Ranking of countries by percentage change in the value of green technological innovation in the period between 2014 and 2021. North Macedonia is in first place for the value of green technological innovation with an amount equal to 961.11% equal to an amount of 25.87 units, in second place is Malta with an amount equal to 567.18% equal to 146.47 units, and from Iceland with a value equal to 77.85% equal to an amount of 25.23 units. In the middle of the table there are Germany with a percentage change equal to an amount of -26.00% equal to an amount of -27.87 units, followed by Spain with an amount of -26.32% equal to an amount of -26.37 units, and from Lithuania with a value of 28.49% equal to an amount of 46.61 units. Bosnia closes the ranking with a value of -74.69% equal to a value of -122.09 units, followed by Romania with a value equal to -84.62% equal to an amount of -80.61 units and by Cyprus with a value of -100.00% equal to an amount of -68.8 units. On average, the value of the percentage change in green technological innovation in the period between 2014 and 2021 for the countries considered decreased by an amount equal to -25.26% equal to an amount of -23.08 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering is then carried out through the use of the k-Means algorithm optimized through the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are thus identified as indicated below, namely:

- Cluster 1: Turkey, Ireland, Slovenia, Iceland, Israel, Switzerland, North Macedonia, Latvia, Montenegro, Cyprus, Belgium, Italy, Malta, Netherlands, Hungary;

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- Cluster 2: Finland, Greece, Slovakia, Germany, Estonia, Lithuania, Serbia, Luxembourg, Spain, Austria, Denmark, Bulgaria, Norway, Bosnia, Ukraine, France, Croatia, Portugal, United Kingdom, Poland, Romania, Czech Republic, Sweden.

Taking into consideration the median of the countries of the clusters, it results that the value of the median of the countries of cluster 1 is equal to an amount of 45.62 while the value of the median of cluster 2 is equal to an amount of 73.93 units. It therefore follows that the ordering of the clusters is $C2 > C1$. From the point of view of green technology, there is therefore a contrast between the countries of cluster 2 which are highly evolved in terms of green tech and the countries of cluster 1 which are more backward.

However, from a geographical point of view there are no distinctions between the cluster 2 countries and the cluster 1 countries of Western Europe. So, the fact that there are countries that produce differentiated levels in terms of green-oriented technological innovations must be understood from the strictly cultural, value and models of technological innovation point of view. The distinction between countries, therefore, manifests a different sensitivity to the environmental dimension rather than a diversity of starting points or technological and scientific endowments.

An alternative method for calculating clustering is the Elbow method. If we apply this method, then it turns out that the optimal number of clusters is not 2 but rather 4. By recalculating the clusters with $k = 4$ using the k-Means algorithm, the following groupings result, namely:

- Cluster 1: Ireland, Israel, Switzerland, Turkey, Cyprus, Belgium, Italy, Slovenia, Hungary, North Macedonia, the Netherlands;
- Cluster 2: Malta, Latvia, Montenegro;
- Cluster 3: Denmark, Estonia, Bosnia, Bulgaria;
- Cluster 4: Germany, Luxembourg, Austria, Spain, Norway, France, Finland, Croatia, Ukraine, United Kingdom, Portugal, Poland, Czech Republic, Greece, Romania, Slovakia, Lithuania, Sweden, Serbia.

Also recalculating the value of the medians of the indicated clusters of the Elbow method the following order is obtained: in first place there are the countries of cluster 3-C3 with a median value equal to 150.71, followed by the countries of cluster 4-C4 with a value of 73.83, from the countries of cluster 1-C1 with a value of 47.06 units, and from the countries of cluster 2-C2 with a value of 14.76 units. The following order therefore derives from it, that is: $C3 > C4 > C1 > C2$. Also, in this case it is not possible to find a clear contrast between highly and poorly evolved countries in the production of tech-green innovations since cluster 4, that is the most populous, is made up of countries both in Southern and Northern Europe. In any case, thanks to this further clustering with the Elbow method it is possible to identify that most European countries tend to be positively oriented towards green technological innovations. There are essentially 3 backward countries, represented in cluster 2-C2, namely Malta, Latvia, and Montenegro.

Network Analysis. A network analysis is carried out below using the Euclidean distance method. Four different one-to-one linkages have therefore been identified, indicated below, namely:

- Portugal and Ukraine are connected in a link with a value of 0.34 units;
- Israel and Switzerland are connected through a link with a value of 0.26 units;
- The Netherlands and Hungary are connected through a link with a value of 0.26 units;
- France and the United Kingdom are connected through a link with a value of 0.36.

These links fail to identify cause and effect links. Rather, they represent internal connections to the historical series dynamics of the data.

Conclusion. In summary, it is possible to verify that on average in European countries the level of green-oriented technological innovation decreased significantly between 2014 and 2021. In fact, in 2014 on average 91.37% of European patents were green oriented, a value that in 2021 became equal to an amount of 68.29%. Therefore, contrary to what is indicated by the macro-plans of the European Union, countries and companies have reduced the green orientation of technological innovations, evidently showing a preference for profit indifferent to the environment rather than economic development with environmentally sustainable innovations.

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Appendix

	2021	Countries	Cluster	Silhouette
1	67.8998	Austria	C4	0.657679
3	57.4307	Belgium	C1	0.595813
2	41.378	Bosnia and Her...	C3	0.559884
4	172.292	Bulgaria	C3	0.534912
15	57.7796	Croatia	C4	0.629842
6	0	Cyprus	C1	0.593125
7	64.5098	Czechia	C4	0.596534
9	164.066	Denmark	C3	0.63348
10	137.345	Estonia	C3	0.550895
13	80.3132	Finland	C4	0.637954
14	74.9789	France	C4	0.646717
8	79.3162	Germany	C4	0.666984
11	73.932	Greece	C4	0.620802
16	48.507	Hungary	C1	0.579747
19	57.6301	Iceland	C1	0.629023
17	22.3342	Ireland	C1	0.665887
18	32.7534	Israel	C1	0.65669
20	59.026	Italy	C1	0.559525
23	14.7565	Latvia	C2	0.55705
21	117.005	Lithuania	C4	0.598364
22	64.9585	Luxembourg	C4	0.656134
26	172.292	Malta	C2	0.564441
24	0	Montenegro	C2	0.513536
27	52.7445	Netherlands	C1	0.570139
25	28.5658	North Macedonia	C1	0.596972
28	56.5333	Norway	C4	0.636932
29	78.9672	Poland	C4	0.618667
30	68.1491	Portugal	C4	0.588562
31	14.6568	Romania	C4	0.585108
32	103.744	Serbia	C4	0.582625
35	124.982	Slovakia	C4	0.608335
34	55.9351	Slovenia	C1	0.581876
12	73.8323	Spain	C4	0.656608
33	83.0053	Sweden	C4	0.575847
5	30.2608	Switzerland	C1	0.656176
36	45.6155	Turkey	C1	0.627454
37	44.3193	Ukraine	C4	0.605567
38	73.3338	United Kingdom	C4	0.627594

Countries	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Austria	★ 105,79	★ 105,79	★ 105,79	★ 105,34	★ 87,64	★ 72,54	★ 75,43	★ 67,90
Bosnia and Herzegovina	★ 163,47	★ 163,47	★ 163,47	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 157,49	★ 29,11	★ 41,38
Belgium	★ 75,28	★ 75,28	★ 75,28	★ 60,62	★ 58,43	★ 66,15	★ 65,96	★ 57,43
Bulgaria	★ 127,37	★ 127,37	★ 127,37	★ 125,88	★ 127,47	★ 142,98	★ 172,29	★ 172,29
Switzerland	★ 63,36	★ 63,36	★ 63,36	★ 58,78	★ 51,35	★ 45,32	★ 38,14	★ 30,26
Cyprus	★ 68,80	★ 68,80	★ 68,80	★ 52,50	★ 31,21	★ 84,25	★ 79,86	★ 0,00
Czechia	★ 95,72	★ 95,72	★ 95,72	★ 79,91	★ 76,87	★ 86,69	★ 64,71	★ 64,51
Germany	★ 107,18	★ 107,18	★ 107,18	★ 103,69	★ 97,11	★ 91,08	★ 85,80	★ 79,32
Denmark	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 169,85	★ 154,10	★ 149,91	★ 164,07
Estonia	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 119,60	★ 93,97	★ 129,72	★ 137,35
Greece	★ 151,05	★ 151,05	★ 151,05	★ 118,25	★ 87,34	★ 91,68	★ 69,64	★ 73,93
Spain	★ 100,20	★ 100,20	★ 100,20	★ 113,02	★ 112,77	★ 100,01	★ 88,29	★ 73,83
Finland	★ 118,95	★ 118,95	★ 118,95	★ 120,25	★ 108,08	★ 100,45	★ 92,88	★ 80,31
France	★ 93,13	★ 93,13	★ 93,13	★ 99,31	★ 97,91	★ 91,13	★ 84,95	★ 74,98
Croatia	★ 97,41	★ 97,41	★ 97,41	★ 114,21	★ 93,37	★ 63,06	★ 59,67	★ 57,78
Hungary	★ 82,91	★ 82,91	★ 82,91	★ 76,62	★ 58,58	★ 44,12	★ 54,94	★ 48,51
Ireland	★ 47,76	★ 47,76	★ 47,76	★ 45,67	★ 41,78	★ 35,89	★ 31,46	★ 22,33
Israel	★ 58,93	★ 58,93	★ 58,93	★ 64,01	★ 51,20	★ 36,99	★ 31,36	★ 32,75
Iceland	★ 32,40	★ 32,40	★ 32,40	★ 15,35	★ 0,85	★ 12,36	★ 29,71	★ 57,63
Italy	★ 72,74	★ 72,74	★ 72,74	★ 76,23	★ 72,09	★ 64,56	★ 64,06	★ 59,03
Lithuania	★ 163,62	★ 163,62	★ 163,62	★ 82,06	★ 93,72	★ 76,47	★ 103,54	★ 117,01
Luxembourg	★ 110,97	★ 110,97	★ 110,97	★ 121,14	★ 74,68	★ 77,47	★ 81,21	★ 64,96
Latvia	★ 15,50	★ 15,50	★ 15,50	★ 60,47	★ 95,47	★ 108,23	★ 87,09	★ 14,76
Montenegro	★ 0,00	★ 0,00	★ 0,00	★ 0,00	★ 105,94	★ 105,94	★ 0,00	★ 0,00
North Macedonia	★ 2,69	★ 2,69	★ 2,69	★ 101,20	★ 62,02	★ 0,00	★ 28,57	★ 28,57
Malta	★ 25,82	★ 25,82	★ 25,82	★ 46,61	★ 94,07	★ 123,14	★ 170,15	★ 172,29
Netherlands	★ 80,71	★ 80,71	★ 80,71	★ 76,32	★ 64,76	★ 54,69	★ 53,99	★ 52,74
Norway	★ 110,52	★ 110,52	★ 110,52	★ 102,65	★ 82,36	★ 59,42	★ 59,67	★ 56,53
Poland	★ 79,22	★ 79,22	★ 79,22	★ 107,38	★ 112,87	★ 99,21	★ 98,71	★ 78,97
Portugal	★ 112,07	★ 112,07	★ 112,07	★ 94,07	★ 74,28	★ 43,07	★ 50,35	★ 68,15
Romania	★ 95,27	★ 95,27	★ 95,27	★ 110,27	★ 126,13	★ 64,91	★ 17,85	★ 14,66
Serbia	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 172,29	★ 125,33	★ 61,32	★ 75,48	★ 95,27	★ 103,74
Sweden	★ 78,27	★ 78,27	★ 78,27	★ 78,07	★ 88,04	★ 100,01	★ 94,87	★ 83,01
Slovenia	★ 33,15	★ 33,15	★ 33,15	★ 53,74	★ 69,45	★ 71,89	★ 58,98	★ 55,94
Slovakia	★ 143,98	★ 143,98	★ 143,98	★ 124,38	★ 76,62	★ 83,10	★ 117,15	★ 124,98
Turkey	★ 28,86	★ 28,86	★ 28,86	★ 32,65	★ 30,06	★ 52,05	★ 57,93	★ 45,62
Ukraine	★ 119,35	★ 119,35	★ 119,35	★ 92,63	★ 65,66	★ 53,24	★ 52,45	★ 44,32
United Kingdom	★ 92,88	★ 92,88	★ 92,88	★ 91,93	★ 86,10	★ 81,81	★ 78,32	★ 73,33

Ranking of countries by percentage change in Green Technological Innovations.							
Rank	Countries	Abs Var	Per Var	Rank	Countries	Abs Var	Per Var
1	North Macedonia	25,87	1061,11	20	Finland	-38,64	67,52
2	Malta	146,47	667,18	21	Czechia	-31,21	67,4
3	Iceland	25,23	177,85	22	Netherlands	-27,97	65,35
4	Slovenia	22,78	168,72	23	Austria	-37,89	64,18
5	Turkey	16,75	158,03	24	Portugal	-43,92	60,81
6	Bulgaria	44,92	135,26	25	Serbia	-68,55	60,21
7	Sweden	4,74	106,05	26	Croatia	-39,63	59,31
8	Poland	-0,25	99,69	27	Luxembourg	-46,01	58,54
9	Denmark	-8,23	95,23	28	Hungary	-34,4	58,51
10	Latvia	-0,75	95,18	29	Israel	-26,17	55,58
11	Slovakia	-18,99	86,81	30	Norway	-53,99	51,15
12	Italy	-13,71	81,15	31	Greece	-77,12	48,94
13	France	-18,15	80,51	32	Switzerland	-33,1	47,76
14	Estonia	-34,95	79,72	33	Ireland	-25,43	46,76
15	United Kingdom	-19,54	78,96	34	Ukraine	-75,03	37,13
16	Belgium	-17,85	76,29	35	Bosnia and Herzegovina	-122,09	25,31
17	Germany	-27,87	74	36	Romania	-80,61	15,38
18	Spain	-26,37	73,68	37	Cyprus	-68,8	0
19	Lithuania	-46,61	71,51	38	Media	-23,08	74,74

Ranking of countries by Green Technological Innovations.

Rank	Countries	2021	Rank	Countries	2021
1	<i>Bulgaria</i>	172,29	19	<i>Italy</i>	59,03
1	<i>Malta</i>	172,29	20	<i>Croatia</i>	57,78
2	<i>Denmark</i>	164,07	21	<i>Iceland</i>	57,63
3	<i>Estonia</i>	137,35	22	<i>Belgium</i>	57,43
4	<i>Slovakia</i>	124,98	23	<i>Norway</i>	56,53
5	<i>Lithuania</i>	117,01	24	<i>Slovenia</i>	55,94
6	<i>Serbia</i>	103,74	25	<i>Netherlands</i>	52,74
7	<i>Sweden</i>	83,01	26	<i>Hungary</i>	48,51
8	<i>Finland</i>	80,31	27	<i>Turkey</i>	45,62
9	<i>Germany</i>	79,32	28	<i>Ukraine</i>	44,32
10	<i>Poland</i>	78,97	29	<i>Bosnia and Herzegovina</i>	41,38
11	<i>France</i>	74,98	30	<i>Israel</i>	32,75
12	<i>Greece</i>	73,93	31	<i>Switzerland</i>	30,26
13	<i>Spain</i>	73,83	32	<i>North Macedonia</i>	28,57
14	<i>United Kingdom</i>	73,33	33	<i>Ireland</i>	22,33
15	<i>Portugal</i>	68,15	34	<i>Latvia</i>	14,76
16	<i>Austria</i>	67,90	35	<i>Romania</i>	14,66
17	<i>Luxembourg</i>	64,96	36	<i>Cyprus</i>	0,00
18	<i>Czechia</i>	64,51	37	<i>Montenegro</i>	0,00

Ranking of countries by Green Technological Innovations.

